

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approach to Sino-Tibetan)

Language contact between Tibetic and Mongolic, with a special focus on the Amdo Linguistic Area

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Abstract: Tibetic and Mongolic languages have been influenced by each other on various levels throughout history. Especially in the Amdo linguistic area, since the migration of the Oirat Mongolian nomads around the 17th century, there has been close cultural contact. Linguistically, both language groups have experienced language contact in both directions. In this paper, we focus on loanwords between Tibetic and Mongolic languages by using a geolinguistic approach. In addition, the Amdo area showcases a distinct preference for words tied to pastoral culture and weaponry. By comparing the general tendency of borrowing in each language group, the characteristics of cultural contact between the Tibetan and Mongolian tribes in the Amdo linguistic area are discussed.*

Keywords: loanwords; Tibetic; Mongolic; Amdo linguistic area

1. Introduction

This study examines language contact between Tibetic (belonging to Tibeto-Burman) and Mongolic by using a geolinguistic approach. Although the language contact between these two language groups at the macro level dates back to the ancient era, this paper focuses on micro-level contact between Tibetic and Mongolic in the Amdo linguistic area (the ‘Amdo Sprachbund’ in Slater 2019). Although language contact in grammatical forms and functions has recently attracted attention in the Amdo linguistic area (Sandman and Simon 2016 etc.), we limit the focus of this discussion only to loanwords between Tibetic and Mongolic.

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The Amdo linguistic area lies on the northeastern edge of the Tibetan plateau. In the modern administrative division, it is located in the eastern Qinghai and southern Gansu provinces. Historical causes, including political and military control, have formed the present situation of language contact among four language groups: Tibetic, Mongolic, Turkic, and Sinitic.

Fig. 1 Amdo Linguistic Area (Iwao & Ikeda 2021)

In the following, we examine loanwords borrowed from Tibetic to Mongolic (§2) and from Mongolic to Tibetic (§3) in turn. In each section, we first discuss the situation in Mongolian- or Tibetan-speaking areas outside Amdo. Next, we discuss the situation inside the area, and then we make a more general comparison, which will identify the characteristics of borrowing in the Amdo area.

2. Tibetic loanwords in Mongolic languages

Because of the long historical and cultural relationship with Tibetans, Mongols have adopted many words from Tibetan.

2.1. Tibetic loanwords in Mongolic languages in general

Many Tibetic words in Mongolic, either of Tibetic origin or borrowed through Tibetic, are related to Buddhism, the names of planets, days of the week, mineral substances, plants, and diseases. Examples include the following:

Written Mongolian (WT)		Written Tibetan (WT)
<i>lama</i>	‘monk, priest’	<i>bla ma</i>
<i>rabsal</i>	‘textbook of minor rites’	<i>rab gsal</i>
<i>jada</i>	‘rainmaking by use of magic spell’	<i>gyad</i>
<i>bumba</i>	‘vessel for holy objects’	<i>bum pa</i>
<i>namtar</i>	‘biography, legend’	<i>rnam thar</i>
<i>diglim</i>	‘order, system’	<i>sgrig lam</i>
<i>maday</i>	‘mistake, fault, error’	<i>ma dag</i>
<i>saya</i>	‘million’	<i>sa ya</i>
<i>bum</i>	‘hundred thousand’	<i>'bum</i>
<i>nima</i>	‘Sunday’	<i>nyi ma</i>
<i>lhayba</i>	‘mercury; Wednesday’	<i>lhag pa</i>
<i>nomin</i>	‘azure stone’	<i>mu men</i>
<i>dorjipalam</i>	‘diamond’	<i>rdo rje pha lam</i>
<i>jay</i>	‘gonorrhoea’	<i>zag</i>
<i>yariγ</i>	‘paralysis, apoplexy’	<i>ka rigs</i>
<i>badayana</i>	‘cancer of the stomach’	<i>bad kan</i>
<i>sügmil</i>	‘cardamom’	<i>sug rmel</i>
<i>buram</i>	‘cane sugar’	<i>bu ram</i>

Most of these words do not seem to have entered Mongolic through everyday contact between local Tibetan and Mongolian commoners.

2.2. Tibetic loanwords in Mongolic languages in Amdo

In the Amdo area, Tibetic and Mongolic people are routinely in contact with one another, and the Mongolic languages spoken in this area have words of Tibetic origin that are not known in other Mongolic languages.

As an example, consider the case of animal vocabulary. Figures 2 to 5 show maps of the geographic distribution of words for ‘wolf’ (Figures 2 and 3) and ‘bear’ (Figures 4 and 5) in Tibetic and Mongolic in general and in Amdo.

The original Mongolic word for ‘wolf’ is *čono*, and this is the term used most widely in Mongolic languages. But, in Amdo, Dongxiang has the word *dzaŋgəi*, and Monguor

uses the form *kadam/kadan*, which are related to Tibetic *hcaŋkhu* and *khadam*, respectively.

The original Mongolic word for ‘bear’ is *bābgai*, but languages in peripheral regions adopt words from their neighboring languages. In the Amdo area, Baoan uses the form *dermoŋ* for ‘bear,’ which is a copy of the Tibetic word *dred mong*.

Fig. 2 ‘Wolf’ in Tibetic and Mongolic (in general)

Fig. 3 ‘Wolf’ in Tibetic and Mongolic (in Amdo)

Fig. 4 'Bear' in Tibetic and Mongolic (in general)

Fig. 5 'Bear' in Tibetic and Mongolic (in Amdo)

2.3. Discussion about Tibetic loanwords in Mongolic languages

Unlike religious and scientific terms, which are used by intellectuals and are independent of region, everyday words adopted from local neighboring languages may be found only in specific areas. The abovementioned Dongxiang, Monguor, and Baoan animal-related words of Tibetic origin are not known to the other Mongolic languages and are found only in the Amdo area, where Tibetans and Mongols are in close proximity.

3. Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic languages

Next, we examine the case where Tibetans have adopted words from Mongols.

3.1. Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic languages in general

Mongolian adopted loanwords in the sphere of religious affairs from Tibetan, whereas Tibetans adopted Mongolian words for secular affairs from the beginning of the Mongol Empire (Laufer 1916; Thubten Jigme Norbu & Takeuchi 1991). Three good examples from these previous studies of categories of Mongolian loanwords in Central Tibet are (1) administrative terms and titles, (2) foreign goods and trade goods, and (3) physicians. Examples include the following:

(1) administrative terms and titles

WT		WM
<i>dza sag</i>	‘Mongolian title’	<i>ḡasaḡ</i>
<i>the ci</i>	‘Mongolian title’	<i>taiḡi</i>
<i>taa la’i</i>	‘Tibetan title’	<i>dalai</i>
<i>er te ni</i>	‘treasure’	<i>erdeni</i> (< Skt. <i>ratna</i>)

(2) foreign goods and trade goods

WT		WM
<i>thob ci</i>	‘button’	<i>tobči</i>
<i>a cor</i>	‘towel’	<i>alčiḡur</i>
<i>’o mo su</i>	‘stocking’	<i>oyimosu</i>

(3) physician

WT		WM
<i>am ci</i>	‘doctor’	<i>emči</i>

3.2. Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic languages in the Amdo Area

Thubten Jigme Norbu and Takeuchi (1991) stated that Mongolian loanwords were not established in Amdo Tibetan, but upon close observation some loanwords can be

found, and they have a tendency to be different from loanwords in Central Tibetan. Similar to the loanwords given by Laufer (1916), terms in group (1) ('administrative terms and titles') are also found in modern Amdo Tibetan. However, as noted by Thubten Jigme Norbu and Takeuchi (1991), loanwords referring to (2) ('foreign goods', such as towels, socks, and buttons) and (3) ('physicians') are not found.

Thubten Jigme Norbu and Takeuchi (1991) mentioned that 'while these Mongolian words have been employed and are still in use in the dialect of Lhasa, these words could not have been established in the dialects of Eastern Tibet, such as the Amdo dialect, even though Amdo is the place where Tibetans and Mongolians live side by side.' However, through fieldwork and a literature survey, we have found different kinds of Mongolian loanwords used in Amdo Tibetan, namely (i) place names, (ii) *ger* (a Mongolian mobile dwelling), (iii) camel names and equipment, (iv) horse tack, (v) natural salt, and (vi) guns. Of these, (ii) to (v) can be summarized as words related to pastoral culture.

An example of a term related to pastoral culture belongs to group (iv) ('horse tack') and refers to 'a cushion under a saddle' made by using felt or grass as stuffing. This cushion is called /hom/ (WT: *hom*) in Amdo Tibetan, originally borrowed from the Mongolian word /xom/ (WM: *qom* 'a piece of felt placed under the pack on a camel'). A second example is 'natural salt'. This salt is not for human consumption, but rather to feed livestock, and it is very important for animal growth and maintaining health. This natural salt is called /hordjor/ (WT: *ho rjor*) in Amdo Tibetan and was borrowed from the Mongolian word /xuǰir/ (WM: *quǰir* 'salt marsh; soda').

We can also examine the geographic distribution of group (vi) ('guns'). The word for gun in Amdo Tibetan is pronounced /wu/ (WT: *bo'u*). The origin of this word is /pao/ ('砲') in Chinese, but according to Janhunen and Kalsang Norbu (1999: 274) it was borrowed from the Mongolic term /bū/. This interpretation is supported by the fact that the aspirated /p^h/ in Chinese does not correspond to the labial-velar approximant /w/ in Amdo Tibetan.

From the perspective of Tibetic languages, seven types of the word for 'gun' were found:

(1) /wu/ type:

Tib. < Mon. < Ch.

(2) /menda/ type: /mentā/ and /ŋēnda/

Compound forms meaning 'fire arrow' (*me mda* (fire arrow) in WT).

(3) /mengko/ type

/me/ corresponds to *me* (fire) in WT.

(4) /trobda/ type

/bda/ corresponds to *mda* ' (arrow) in WT.

(5) /nda/ type

/nda/ corresponds to *mda* ' (arrow) in WT.

(6) /tubaq/ type

/tubaq/ is of Persian origin and might be borrowed from Turkic (/tüfek/). Tib. < Tur. < Per.

(7) /ts^hu/ type

/ts^hu/ is a loan from the Chinese *qiang* ('槍').

Fig. 6 'Gun' in Tibetic and Mongolic (in general)

Fig. 7 ‘Gun’ in Tibetic and Mongolic (in Amdo)

3.3. Discussion about Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic languages

A comparison of Mongolian loanwords in Central Tibetan and Amdo suggests that there are differences in the way Mongolian and Tibetan speakers interact in each area. In Central Tibet, words related to administration and titles, foreign goods and trade goods, and physicians were borrowed, whereas in Amdo, words related to pastoral culture and guns were found to be distinctive borrowings (Table 1). This suggests that, in Amdo, the Mongolian and Tibetan peoples shared skills related to daily life while living in close proximity to each other.

Table 1 Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic (Central and Amdo Tibetan)

Loanwords	Central Tibetan	Amdo Tibetan
(1) Administrative terms and titles	○	○
(2) Foreign goods, and trade goods	○	—
(3) Physicians	○	—
(4) Pastoral goods	—	○
(5) Gun	—	○

4. Conclusions

This paper has delved into the intricate dynamics of contact between the Tibetic and Mongolic languages, with a specific focus on loanwords within the Amdo linguistic area. Throughout history, the interaction between these two language groups has manifested itself in various ways, leaving traces of cultural exchange and linguistic borrowing. The Amdo area, situated on the northeastern fringes of the Tibetan plateau, has witnessed sustained cultural contact due to historical migrations and geopolitical factors, resulting in a unique linguistic landscape.

The analysis of loanwords highlights the multifaceted nature of this contact. In the case of Tibetic loanwords in Mongolic languages, the borrowing tends to revolve around religious and scientific terminology, reflecting the cultural and intellectual interchange between the two groups. Additionally, everyday words of Tibetic origin find their way into the Mongolic languages spoken within the Amdo area, demonstrating the influence of proximity and routine interaction on vocabulary adoption.

Conversely, an examination of Mongolic loanwords in Tibetic languages, especially in Amdo, unveils a fascinating pattern. Whereas traditional loanwords in Central Tibetan encompass administrative terms, foreign goods, and more, the Amdo area showcases a distinct preference for words tied to pastoral culture and weaponry. This divergence underscores the sociocultural implications of linguistic contact, suggesting that the close coexistence of Tibetan and Mongolian peoples in Amdo has led to the sharing of practical skills relevant to their daily lives.

The geographic distribution of certain loanwords, such as the term for gun, further underscores the intricate web of borrowing. The diversity in borrowing patterns between Central Tibetan and Amdo Tibetan suggests varying modes of interaction and cultural exchange in these areas.

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